

QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART XV

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Synthesis of a thiazylaminoquinoline derivative containing a piperidino group is described.

In recent years certain quinoline and isoquinoline derivatives (Kreitmair, *Arch. Exp. Path. Pharm.*, 1932, 164, 509; Ellinger *et al.*, *Klin Woch*, 1934, 13, 411; German Patent, 549,967) have been found to possess antispasmodic activity. Of the former, reference is made to the synthesis of some pyridylquinolines and thiazylquinolines (Heilbron and co-workers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 401), some of which have shown some promise as spasmolytic agents. That the presence of sulphur-containing groups like thiazyl, thienyl, etc., may promote such activity is indicated by the recent observations (Blicke and Tsao, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 1645; Adamson and Green, *Nature*, 1950, 165, 122) about the pronounced spasmolytic activity of certain thiophene derivatives containing tertiary bases.

From a general survey of the chemistry of antispasmodics (cf. Blicke *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 93, 771, 774) it is found that they are, in general, salts of secondary or tertiary bases. It has been therefore considered to be of interest to synthesise quinoline derivatives containing both the thiazylamino group and tertiary bases and to see if antispasmodic activity might be found in such a class of compounds.

2-Methyl-4-hydroxy-6-aminoquinoline (Jacini, *Gazzetta*, 1939, 69, 111; Kermack and Weatherhead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 563) has now been converted into the corresponding 6-thiocarbamido derivative (I), which, when reacted with $\alpha\beta$ -dichlorodiethyl ether, has easily furnished the corresponding 6-(thiazyl-2'-)amino derivative (II). When treated with phosphorus oxychloride, the compound (II) has yielded the corresponding 4-chloro derivative (III). The condensation of (III) with piperidine results in the formation of the corresponding 4-piperidino derivative (IV) (cf. Kermack and Weatherhead, *loc. cit.*), the pharmacological examination of which is in progress.

(IV)

Compounds other than ketones, but containing an active methyl or methylene group, may sometimes be induced to respond to the Mannich reaction (cf. Kermack and Muir, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 3089; Pathak and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 371). In fact, Kermack and Muir (*loc. cit.*) have shown that the methyl group in quinaldine reacts with formaldehyde and secondary amines to give rise to tertiary bases. In order to introduce another tertiary base into (IV), the condensation of (IV) with formaldehyde and a secondary amine was attempted under a variety of conditions but without success.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

2-Methyl-4-hydroxy-6-thiocarbamidoquinoline (I).—To an aqueous solution of 2-methyl-4-hydroxy-6-aminoquinoline hydrochloride (12 g., Jacini, *loc. cit.*) potassium thiocyanate (10 g.) was added. The solution was heated on the water-bath to dryness and the solid treated with water. The mixture was again evaporated to dryness. This operation was repeated once more and the solid finally baked on the water-bath for 1 hour. The solid was finely powdered, triturated with cold dilute hydrochloric acid, filtered and thoroughly washed with water. It is insoluble in boiling water and in almost all organic solvents, and could not therefore be further crystallised. It was therefore washed thoroughly with hot alcohol and ether and obtained as a yellowish granular solid (11 g.) which decomposes at 270°-272°, with evolution of gas, to a brown pasty solid. (Found: N, 17.71. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_2S$ requires N, 18.02 per cent).

It is insoluble in cold dilute hydrochloric acid but readily soluble in cold dilute alkali. It is rather unstable even towards cold dilute alkali, the conversion into 6-amino-compound taking place within a short time.

2-Methyl-4-hydroxy-6 (thiazyl-2'-) aminoquinoline (II).—The above compound (I, 10 g.) was thoroughly triturated with water (100 c.c.) and while the mixture was heated under reflux on the water-bath, 2β-dichlorodiethyl ether (10 g.) was gradually added under shaking. On heating and shaking a clear solution was gradually obtained which was further heated on the water-bath for 2 hours. Next day the solution was diluted with water and basified with ammonium hydroxide when a brown solid was obtained. It was purified by solution in cold dilute hydrochloric acid, shaking the clear solution with ether and by basifying the aqueous solution with ammonium hydroxide. The brown granular solid (9.2 g.), thus obtained, is practically insoluble in boiling water and in most of the organic solvents. It was, however, crystallised from nitrobenzene as a brownish crystalline powder. It becomes deep chocolate coloured on heating and does not melt even at 300°. (Found: N, 16.68; S, 11.97. $C_{13}H_{11}ON_2S$ requires N, 16.34; S, 12.45 per cent).

The compound (II) is not readily soluble in cold dilute alkali but goes into solution on standing. It is, however, readily soluble in cold dilute hydrochloric acid. In acetic acid the compound is readily soluble and is not precipitated on dilution with water, indicating the formation of a salt with acetic acid. However, the base is completely precipitated when basified with ammonium hydroxide. The solution of the compound in nitrobenzene does not desulphurise yellow oxide of mercury, indicating the presence of sulphur in the ring and the formation of the thiazole ring.

2-Methyl-4-Chloro-6-(thiazyl-2'-)aminoquinoline (III).—The compound (II, 12 g.) was gradually added to phosphorus oxychloride (50 c.c.), when a thick solution was obtained with rise in temperature. The solution was heated in an oil-bath under reflux at 120°-125° for 2 hours and at 125°-130° for a further period of 2 hours. Next day, the excess of phosphorus oxychloride was distilled under reduced pressure and the residue, after being cooled in ice, was treated with cold water when a dark coloured solution was obtained with rise in temperature. The solution was basified with caustic soda solution, when a solid was precipitated which, after being allowed to stand for one hour under occasional stirring, was filtered and thoroughly washed with water. It is readily soluble in alcohol, ether and other organic solvents and was crystallised from aqueous alcohol (charcoal) in yellowish rectangular plates (8 g.), m.p. 206°-207°. It was dried at 105°-110° *in vacuo*. (Found: N, 15.25. $C_{13}H_{10}N_2ClS$ requires N, 15.25 per cent). It is readily soluble in cold, dilute mineral acids but insoluble in alkali.

2-Methyl-4-piperidino-6-(thiazyl-2'-)aminoquinoline (IV).—A mixture of the compound (III, 5 g.) and piperidine (7.5 c.c.) was heated on the water-bath for 4 hours. The thick, dark coloured solution was poured into water when a pasty mass was precipitated. The mixture was steam-distilled and the residue was cooled and powdered. The solid was further purified by solution in dilute hydrochloric acid and reprecipitation by ammonium hydroxide. It was finally crystallised from acetone-benzene mixture (1:1) in brown, rectangular plates (2.8 g.), m.p. 238-40°. (Found: N, 16.95. $C_{18}H_{20}N_4S$ requires N, 17.28 per cent). It is insoluble in alkali but readily soluble in dilute mineral acids. It is soluble in most of the organic solvents but practically insoluble in boiling water.